

The Status of Library Anxiety Among Library and Information Science Students: A Case of Universities in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan

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Cite this Article:

Bashar, K., Jan, R., Hussain, M., & Jan, S. U. (2024). The Status of Library Anxiety Among Library and Information Science Students: A Case of Universities in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. *The Regional Tribune*, 3(1), 129–140.

<https://doi.org/10.63062/trt/V24.027>

ABSTRACT:

The purpose of the current study was to measure the level of library anxiety among library and information science students in the universities of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. The total number of populations was 532. The data were collected from a sample of 207 through stratified simple random sampling because of various programs in the LIS discipline. The study used a quantitative, descriptive survey method using the Library Anxiety Scale questionnaire to collect data from the respondents. The AQAK library anxiety instrument was used to measure the respondents' library anxiety level and significance differences with respect to respondents' gender and their program of study. The overall status of the study also found that the respondents' library anxiety level with respect to "Information resources" was higher among LIS students than other factors. This study also reported that no significant difference was found between male and female students with respect to library anxiety. However, the library anxiety mean score for the BS students was higher than that of M. Phil/MS students, but few differences were found between M.Phil/MS and MLIS students. This study suggests that updated information may be provided to the LIS students, and an information literacy program should be arranged for the newly enrolled students in LIS to decrease the level of library anxiety.

KEY WORDS:

Library Anxiety, Science Students, University, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Education

Introduction

Libraries have a fundamental role in students' learning and academic careers (Jan et al., 2016). The role of libraries is undeniable, whether it is in academic and research activities or in grooming and persuading students. Libraries always assist students in their learning process. As a result, the majority of students benefit from these libraries and, thus, equip themselves for the coming challenges of life. To get the best of it, the students are required to be capable of using the library to find out, to have easy access, and to grab information (Grimes & Charters, 2000). However, most students may not feel free to use library resources. These hurdles and issues lagged behind in fully utilizing library resources, which resulted in students' frustration and anxiety (Mallon, 1986).

Anxiety is a state of human feeling characterized by tense feelings, anxious thoughts, and physical changes. It is believed that the consequences of anxiety are different from person to person, depending upon the nerves of every individual.

On the other hand, students in an educational setting may experience a range of anxiety related to their academic setting, which can be highly stressful. Library anxiety is one of the most common types of academic anxiety. For the first time, in 1986, the said fears and negative feelings about library services among students were noted and identified as library anxiety (Mellon, 1986).

Library anxiety is a bad experience marked by excessive worry, self-defeating, tension, fear, and psychological arousal during the normal library tasks cycle (Jiao & Onwuegbuzie, 2004). It has also been defined as an unpleasant mood or emotional disposition that occurs in a library context and has cognitive, affective, and behavioral consequences (Jiao & Onwuegbuzie, 1999). It is also known as situational anxiety, and it is characterized by worry and emotionality (Jiao et al., 1996).

Given Mellon's work, Kuhlthau (1988) points out students' confusion and hurdles, especially in the early stages of the library search process. It was later identified that the students' library frustration was mostly due to their unfamiliarity with library resources and technologies (Kuhlthau, 1988). Several studies on library anxiety have been conducted, such as the LAS (library anxiety scale) developed by Bostick (1992) and AQAK by Anwar et al. (2012), through which Students can improve their academic needs by using effective library and its resources quite easily. For this purpose, they just need to learn the use of library resources and consult library staff to discuss their information need, and thus, feelings of negativities can be overcome ahead. Thus, the study is conducted with the mental stress and hurdles of not knowing the procedure of library use by students in universities of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa kept in mind.

Literature Review

Generally, literature has identified that library anxiety is always an obstacle for the users of library in different disciplines. A number of research works have been conducted on library anxiety in different parts of the world, including Pakistan. The brief account of those is provided below.

Constance A. Mellon initiated the concept of library anxiety in 1986 when she used the term for the first time after conducting a two-year qualitative study. Later, in 1992, Bostick developed the first Library Anxiety Scale, and since then, extensive work has been done by different researchers on various dimensions, with some researchers basing their scales on the Bostick Library Anxiety Scale as well as other scales. The chapter discusses a review of some key and relevant publications.

Shahbazi et al. (2022) conducted a study on the association between library anxiety and emotional intelligence. Descriptive correlational was used in this study. Graduates of Azarbaijan Shahid Madani University and Tabriz University of Iran participated in the study. Data were collected using the Random sampling method. Siberia Schering's Emotional Intelligence and "Library Anxiety Questionnaire were administered as data instruments. The study revealed that the emotional intelligence scores of both universities were high. Furthermore, they found that library anxiety was 17% of changes to emotional intelligence, while 83% of students' library anxiety was reported for other reasons.

Adeeko and Adetimirin (2022) carried out a study to find the library anxiety of undergraduate students in north-central Nigerian universities. Seven hundred ninety-seven students were selected as a sample from a population of 15933. The measuring Scale on library anxiety (MSLA) developed by Bostick was used as a tool for measuring library anxiety. Their finding showed that the majority of undergraduate students (85%) possessed

moderate library anxiety. The most predominant factor of library anxiety was insufficient knowledge about the library and its resources.

Ismail et al. (2022) carried out a study to determine the level of library anxiety among management science students at the undergraduate level of the University of Peshawar using the AQAK Library Anxiety Scale. Two hundred sixty-two students were selected for data gathering. The study found that final-year students reported the lowest level of library anxiety compared to first-year students. The study further indicated a higher level of library frustration in females than males on a gender basis. Factor-wise, library anxiety revealed that library staff is a main contributor to students' fear and frustration. Furthermore, they concluded that the students belong to rural areas where the majority of schools have no library system or poor library system, which contributed to a high level of library anxiety.

Gogoi et al. (2021) conducted a study on the three different universities in Assam province of India. One hundred fifty students were selected from these three universities for data collection as a sample. The technique adopted for this study was stratified random sampling. The AQAK Library Anxiety Scale was used to find the level of library anxiety. One hundred nineteen questionnaires were returned from the students and fit for data analysis. The findings of the study showed that factors such as gender and language of instruction. Cast and culture do not affect library anxiety. Furthermore, they found that the type of university affects the anxiety of students. No significant difference was found on the basis of gender and language of instructions casts and communities. They stress improving information literacy skills and staff availability of library resources.

(Ahmad et al., 2021) studied the library anxiety of Khyber Medical College (KMC) undergraduate medical students. They used the AQAK Library Anxiety Scale as an instrument to measure K.M.C Students' library anxiety. They found that, overall, students have mild levels of anxiety. The result showed that K.M.C Students have slightly high anxiety for library staff and user education factors. Furthermore, no substantial difference was found on gender basis in the level of library anxiety of responders. It showed that first-year students were found to be more anxious than final-year students.

Asghar et al. (2021) carried out a study to determine the library anxiety level of graduate students of LIS Discipline in universities working in the public sector. The total number of respondents selected for data collection was 511 students of MLIS studying in various library schools in Pakistan. The data was collected through the census method. The instrument used for the data collection was the multidimensional Library Anxiety Scale (Van Kampen, 2003). The result showed that LIS students possessed an overall mild level of anxiety on six factors of MLAS, having a range of 3.35. No difference was found in LIS students on gender basis and frequency of library use.

Popoola and Olajide, (2021) carried out a comparative study on the impact of library anxiety computer skills on the use of library services and resources in southwest Nigeria. The population of the study was 335 undergraduate students of Business administration in private universities. The researcher adopted a correlational survey design. The Multidimensional Library Anxiety Scale and Library Information Resources scale were used as instruments for the collection of data. A substantial association was recorded between computer skills, library anxiety, and library resources used by the participants. Undergraduates with a better understanding of computer literacy skills tend to use library information resources in a better way than those with weak or no computer skills.

Abdoh (2021) carried out a comparative study to find the level of library anxiety between Omani students and Saudi students at the University of South Carolina, USA. A mixed method was used for the collection of data. The AQAK scale was used to measure the level of library anxiety. The result showed that the students reported less library anxiety when they participated in the library orientation program as compared to those who did not attend the library training program. Further, he added that affective barriers and library knowledge barriers were recorded

as the highest levels of library anxiety. No statistical differences were found between males and females on the basis of six variables.

Bushra et al. (2021) carried out a study to explore the library anxiety level of graduate students of the LIS Discipline admitted to nine public sector universities in Pakistan. The Multidimensional Library Anxiety Scale was used to collect data from the respondents. The total number of students was 511 from different LIS departments using census methods. The study revealed that library and information science students possessed a mild level of library anxiety due to all six factors. Further, they investigated that students possessed the highest level of frustration with the information search process and general library anxiety. No statistical differences were found in library anxiety levels of different semesters. No difference was reported on a gender basis. Furthermore, the presence of higher anxiety in the students of Bahauddin Zakariya University, in contrast to Khushal Khan Khattak University Karak, was recorded.

Shehata and Elglab (2019) conducted a comparative study of Egyptian and Saudi Arabian undergraduate students to measure library anxiety. A mixed-method strategy was used in this study. Several students in Saudi Arabia and Egypt participated in semistructured interviews to determine the key elements that contribute to library anxiety. According to the findings, Egyptian students were more anxious to use libraries than Saudi Arabian students. The finding also revealed that in order to reduce anxiety, bibliographical instruction must provide the students with training on how to use libraries.

Ansari (2017) conducted a quantitative study using a modified version of Bostick's (1992) library anxiety scale (LAS) on 367 undergraduate students of the International University of Malaysia. The study employed a stratified random sample technique. His study findings revealed that Malaysian students have a higher level of library anxiety than non-Malaysian students in terms of library limitations, as well as the same amount of anxiety in terms of library employees, library environment, and handling library technology. Furthermore, male students have higher levels of anxiety than females. There was no difference in anxiety levels between students who were guided about bibliographic instructions and those who were not guided about bibliographical instructions.

(Jan et al., 2017). observed the connection between emotional intelligence and library anxiety. The study revealed that students could overcome their negative feelings about the library if the students, regardless of gender, were capable of recognizing, classifying, understanding, and recognizing (Perceiving), handling, and using their own emotions regardless of academic discipline or cultural background.

Research Questions

Keeping in view the purpose of the study, the following research questions were posed:

- (1) What is the overall level of library anxiety among the LIS students?
- (2) What is the factor-wise level of library anxiety among LIS students?
- (3) Is there any difference in the overall level of library anxiety among them based on their various demographic information?

Methodology

A quantitative research approach based on the survey was used, which was the best option for this study. The total population of this research study comprised 532 LIS students of the three public universities of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, namely the University of Peshawar, Khushal Khan Khattak University, Karak and Sarhad University of Science and Technology, Peshawar. The sample size of the study included 226 participants using the Krejcie & Morgan (1970) table. A stratified random sampling technique was used to collect the data from the respondents. The sample of this study consisted of three strata: BS-LIS students, MLIS students, and M. Phil /MS students. Then, simple random sampling was applied within each stratum.

AQAK library anxiety scale was used as an instrument for measuring the level of library anxiety because it was reliable in previous studies (Anwar et al., 2024). AQAK consists of 40 statements assembled based on 5 factors, *i.e., library staff, informational resources, user knowledge, library environment, and user education*. In the current research, the overall reliability score of AQAK was $\alpha = .85$, which is a good reliability score.

Major Findings

Demographic Information

The data given in Table 1 shows that the number of male respondents were 54.6 and female respondents were 45.6. The frequency of library visits and age-wise distribution data shows that the students with 18-21 years were 12.1%, 21-25 years were 19.3%, 25-30 years were 46.4%, and students with 31 and above years were 22.2%. The details of the program-wise distribution of the respondents show that 13.5% (n=28) were B.S LIS students, 53.6% (n=111) were M.L.I.S, and 32.9% were M.Phil/MS students.

Table 1

Gender-wise distribution of the respondents (N= 207)

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	113	54.6%
Female	94	45.4%
Age(years)	Frequency	Percent
18-21	25	12.1
22-25	40	19.3
26-30	96	46.4
31-above	46	22.2
Program of Study	Frequency	Percent
BS LIS	87	42%
MLIS	70	33.8%
MS/M.phil	50	24.2%

Result of Overall Library Anxiety of the Respondents

Research Q.1 explored the overall status of library anxiety of the participants. The data in Table 2 indicates that overall mean score of library anxiety for 207 respondents, which is 3.45 with a standard deviation of on AQAK library anxiety scale. This score falls on the range of mild anxiety. Thus, it can be concluded that on an average all the L.I.S students of three universities possessed mild library anxiety.

Table 2

Descriptive statistics of overall library anxiety (N=207)

Statistics	
Mean	Std. Deviation
3.45	0.43

Result of Factor-wise Library Anxiety of the Respondents

Table 3 presents the statistics for five sub-factors of library anxiety, including library staff, information resources, user education, user knowledge, and library environment. The respondents, with a mean score of 3.67, depicted a

high level of anxiety with regard to the factor 'information sources,' followed by 'Library Environment' with a mean score of 3.58, while for 'User Knowledge' mean score was 3.32, which is the least score among all factors and the reason for this might be that LIS students possess knowledge of the library.

Table 3

Descriptive statistics of factor-wise library anxiety (N=207)

Factor of LA	Mean	(S.D)	Min	Max
Information resource	3.67	.55	2.00	4.83
Library environment	3.58	.55	2.14	5.00
Library staff	3.46	.51	2.30	4.90
User education	3.39	.50	2.00	5.00
User knowledge	3.32	.60	2.00	4.50

Results of overall Library Anxiety of the Respondents on the Gender basis

The data concerning the gender-wise level of overall respondents' library anxiety is shown in Table 4. The statistics found no difference in the overall library anxiety was found on the basis of gender on the AQAK library anxiety scale. The female recorded 3.42 with a standard deviation of 0.40, while male students recorded 3.45 with a standard deviation of 0.45.

Table 4

Gender-wise descriptive statistics for overall library anxiety along with t-test

Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Sig. (2Tailed)
Male	113	3.47	0.45	0.390
Female	94	3.42	0.40	

Statistically Significant (p<.05)

Results of Factor-wise Library Anxiety of the Respondents on the Basis of Gender

The data concerning on the basis of gender for factor-wise library anxiety of the respondents is presented in Table 5. The results of the analysis shows that no significant difference was found for any factors of library anxiety according to the gender of the respondents.

Table 5

Gender-wise descriptive statistics for factor-wise library anxiety, along with a t-test

Factor of LA	Gender	N	Mean	S. D
Library staff	Male	113	3.47	.51
	Female	94	3.45	.47
User education	Male	113	3.35	.49
	Female	94	3.33	.51
Information resources	Male	113	3.67	.55
	Female	94	3.67	.55
User knowledge	Male	113	3.38	.59
	Female	94	3.36	.59
library environment	Male	113	3.58	.57
	Female	94	3.57	.52

Results of Library Anxiety on the Basis of Program of Study

Research Q3 examined the library anxiety of LIS students on the basis of the program of study of the respondents.

Overall Library Anxiety on the Basis of Program of Study

Table 6 represents the result of overall library anxiety on the basis of the program of study, in which the respondents with different LIS programs of study were compared on their overall library anxiety score to find out the difference in this regard. The overall library anxiety mean score for the B.S. students was relatively higher (M=3.61, SD = 0.42), while the overall library anxiety mean score of the MS/M. Phil was lower (3.15, SD=0.43) on the table. This means that B. S. students were more anxious than MS. M. Phil level LIS students. The overall mean score for M.L.I. S-level students (M=3.36, SD=0.33. It was closer to MS. M. Phil, showing that there was minimal difference in their overall level of library anxiety. However, for further endorsement, one-way ANOVA was applied to check the significant difference in this regard.

Table 6

Overall library anxiety based on the basis of the program of STUDY

Program of study	Mean	Std. Deviation
MS/M.Phil	3.15	0.43
M.L.I. S	3.36	0.33
B. S	3.61	0.42

The mean score of overall library anxiety with three different groups was B.S, M.L.I.S, and MS/M. Phil of L.I.S was calculated on the basis of one-way ANOVA. The criterion of 0.5 significance was used, and the *p*-value was reported in this respect. The result shows that there was a statistically significant difference between the mean scores of the two groups for overall library anxiety, as shown in Table 7. Further analysis was elaborated with the help of a posthoc (HSD) test of One-Way ANOVA that revealed the significant difference regarding overall library anxiety level between B.S L.I. S and MS/M. Phil students, with *p*= .000, met the criteria of a 0.5 level. It shows that B.S. students have a high level of anxiety as compared to MS/MPhil level students. Similarly, BS LIS students have a high level of anxiety as compared to MLIS students. The reason for this result might be the fact that MS/M. Phil and MLIS students have more experience and acquaintance with library resources, the environment, and their use compared to B.S. level students, as they are new to library resources, the environment, and their use.

Table 7

Overall library anxiety: program of study-wise one-way ANOVA multiple (post hoc) comparison (N=207)

Multiple Comparisons			
(I)Program of Study	(J) Program of Study	Mean Difference (I-J)	Sig (P value)
B.S	M.L.I. S	-.25224*	.000
B. S	M.S/M.Phil.	-.46310*	.000
M.S/M.Phi.l	M.S/M.Phil.	-.21085	.031

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Discussion

In this part of the study, a detailed discussion of its results was conducted by comparing them with the findings of the earlier studies. Students in various Universities possess high levels of frustration and anxiety that have been identified by international research. The present era belongs to information technology and innovations, and libraries

are shifting from conventional methods and techniques to the latest and up-to-date techniques in order to make the information available to their students and researchers in a more modern and sophisticated manner. Such information explosion makes the students worried about the library, and with this work in hand, it is presumed that library anxiety also exists among LIS students. The result of this study revealed that the students of LIS of three universities in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa have a mild level of library anxiety $M=3.45$ with 0.43 standard deviation related to the overall five factors.

The result of this study supported the results of Rehman et al. (2015) because their result showed that mild levels of library anxiety have been found in undergraduate students of the University of Punjab, Lahore. This research work also established uniformity with the findings of Anwar et al. (2004); the findings of their result confirmed the presence of mild library anxiety in the majority of students (72%). This finding also confirmed the findings of Anwar, Jan and Warraich (2017). Their findings also showed that a majority (72.1%) of the undergraduate university students possessed mild library anxiety in their study.

The factor-wise library of the respondents was also measured, and the result indicated a moderate level of library anxiety for information resources and library environments. While a mild level of anxiety has been reported for library staff, user education, and user knowledge in all LIS students., the reason for this might be that libraries in these universities do not acquire and maintain sufficient relevant and up-to-date materials in the subject area of LIS.

The result of this study showed similarity in the three factors, User Education, User Knowledge, and Library staff, with the finding of the study of Rehman et al. (2015), as their result showed that undergraduate students of the University of Punjab, Lahore possessed a mild level of library anxiety while the results of the two factors Information.

Resources and Library Environment had a moderate level of library anxiety. This research work also established a consistency with the finding of Anwar et al. (2004); the finding of their result showed that the majority of students (72%) at Kuwait University possessed a mild level of library anxiety in factors of User Education, User Knowledge, and Library staff. At the same time, it was contracted with regard to the factors of information resources and the library environment. This finding also confirmed the findings of Anwar, Jan, and Warraich (2016). Their finding also showed that a majority (72.1%) of the undergraduate university students possessed mild library anxiety in their study. This study also shows consistency with the Atlas (2005) Confirmed a high level of frustration among the students about factor information resources.

The third objective of the study was to explore the students' library anxiety regarding various demographic characteristics. In this regard, gender-wise, statistically significant differences in library anxiety were checked. The mean score for overall library anxiety of male students was ($M=3.47$ $SD=0.45$), while the mean score for overall library anxiety of female students was ($M=3.42$, $SD=0.40$), having a small difference. Moreover, there was little difference in the mean scores of male students and female students on gender bases. No statistically significant difference was found in the mean scores of the male and female students with regard to factors of library anxiety. The finding regarding overall library anxiety was contradicted by the finding of (Warraich, 2016), who reported that male students were more anxious than female undergraduate students. This finding also shows dissimilarity with that of Jiao & Onwuegbuzie (1997), who reported that male students had a higher level of library anxiety than female students. This study supported the study of Rehman et al. (2015), who reported that there was no statistically significant gender-based difference in library anxiety scores of undergraduate students of the University of the Punjab, Lahore. The findings of the current study disagree with the findings of Shoham and Mizarchi (2015), who found a statistically important difference between male and female B. Ed students.

Another demographic characteristic of the third objective of this study was to explore the statistically significant difference between the library anxiety score overall and also library anxiety score factor-wise on the basis of the Program. Program-wise demographic factor, the mean score of overall library anxiety for the students of B.S

($M=3.61$, $SD=0.42$) was higher than MLIS students ($M=3.36$, $SD=0.33$ and MS/MPhil ($M=3.15$, $SD=0.43$), where there is a gradual decrease from B.S to MS/M.phil level of study. This gradual decrease in the students' library anxiety score seems to be the result of the frequent use of the library, which involves the students in class assignments and research projects, which might compel them to use the library. One-way ANOVA was also applied to the mean score of the overall level of library anxiety and the five factors of library anxiety of the B.S. students, MLIS, and MS/M. Phil students to know the statistically significant differences among the levels of anxiety of LIS students of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. The results of multiple post hoc comparisons indicated that there was a statistically significant difference in the mean score of BS students in comparison to both MLIS students and MS/M.Phil students with respect to overall and factor-wise library anxiety. This finding disagrees with the findings of Casanova and Tait (2014), who found no statistically substantial relationship in the magnitude of library anxiety based on years of study by the respondents. The findings of the current study supported the findings of Shoham and Mizarchi (2015), who found a statistically important difference between the years of study of B. Ed's students and library anxiety. The findings of the current study were consistent with the outcomes of Rehman et al. (2015), who described significant differences in the level of library anxiety based on the respondents' level of study (semester-wise) through the results of one-way ANOVA post hoc Tukey test. They stated that students of 1st semester had significantly higher 'user education' anxiety than the students of 2nd semester and 4th semester.

Conclusion & Recommendations

Conclusions

The review of the literature shows lack of library anxiety research in Pakistan in particular and in developing countries in general. The present study designed to explore the phenomena of library anxiety among the LIS of three university of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. A 40-item library anxiety scale of AQAK by Anwar et al. (2012) was used in this research with CA internal reliability of 0.80. The finding also indicated that the majority of the students ($n=111$) who participated in the survey were of the MLIS. The findings for the overall library anxiety suggested that the students of LIS students of three universities in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa possess mild library anxiety. The findings for overall library anxiety also showed that female students have shown little higher anxiety than their male counterparts, and in the case of factor-wise library anxiety, the students were more anxious for information resources than the other factors. These findings have many implications. The absence of library instructional programs may have caused mild library anxiety among the students. Similarly, because of the availability of information resources in English medium, the English language is not the native language of the students. Similarly, the information explosion among the students of information science and library is also a reason for library anxiety. Having library anxiety in the students may also impact other areas, such as avoiding visiting the library or the non-use of the library, leading the students to poor achievements in their respective academic careers.

In addition, a t-test was applied to determine the statistically significant differences based on gender for overall library anxiety as well as for factor-wise library anxiety of the students. The results indicated that there were no statistically substantial differences based on gender.

The findings related to the programs of study-wise level for overall and factor-wise library anxiety revealed that a relatively high level of anxiousness was found in the B. S students as compared to the M. Phil/MS students. The finding of one-way ANOVA demonstrated that statistically substantial variations were found in the overall library anxiety level as well as the factor-wise library anxiety score of the students based on the study program. Despite frequent library instructional programs, it is very satisfying that the students of LIS have relatively lower levels of library anxiety as they progress in their study level. Thus, it can be concluded that the optimum utilization of library resources produces better results in the academic performance of the students. Moreover, it helps students to be

free from library anxiety. Furthermore, university results indicated that KKKUK students are more anxious than UoP and SUIT because of the reason that KKKUK constitute more BS students as compared to UoP and SUIT.

Recommendations

1. On the basis of the present study, it is strongly recommended that a library orientation program be conducted for the students of LIS, especially B.S students, as they have no or little previous experience of library use.
2. It is also recommended that different workshops and seminars be conducted to raise awareness of the HEC database, electronic resources, and different searching techniques in time to make the students.
3. Most students are anxious about library resources; therefore, it is strongly recommended that library services be provided at the school level to help them use the library resources.
4. It is also recommended that LIS departments of universities of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa arrange information literacy programs for the newly enrolled students of the B.S. program, which will produce better results in user education improvement. Moreover, it will also serve as a tool for students to lower their anxiety with regard to library staff.
5. AQAK library anxiety scale was found suitable for all levels of programs of study as this study includes the population of undergraduates and post-graduates.
6. It is also suggested that the teaching faculty should guide the students about the worth of library for good academic achievement and also involve them in library-related activities through projects and assignments so that they regularly visit the library and utilize the library resources. This will have definite impact on their library anxiety level.
7. It is also recommended that the environment of the library must be good and attractive, there must be enough space and it must be clean and should provide every facility to the students. Then it will attract students and will reduce their anxiety level.
8. It is further recommended that the libraries of departments of LIS of the three universities of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa acquire and maintain sufficient relevant and up-to-date materials in the subject area of LIS to fulfill the requirements of the LIS Students.

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